

Dark Energy and Multiverse

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The James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) has identified distant galaxies that are much more evolved than our current Cosmological Model predicts, e.g. Galaxy JADES-GS-z14-0. A new Cosmological Model "Dark Energy-Multiverse" is presented in this article. The new model is expected to explain Cosmological Principle better than current "Lambda-CDM"-model. "Dark Energy-Multiverse"-model presents a new approach to Dark Energy and introduces a Multiverse-model that is able to explain distant galaxies identified by JWST and the reason why Universe's expansion rate is increasing. Multiverse-model assumes that our Universe is a part of bigger volume of spacetime; i.e. part of the Multiverse. Updated model of Dark Energy is able to explain Dark Matter problem, Hubble Tension and Gravitation. Updated Dark Energy model is based on Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) and updated Dark Matter model is based on Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND). "Dark Energy-Multiverse"-model makes predictions on Superstructure-findings in Multiverse, measurement of the Inflation size of the Universe and measurement of the Milky Way Galaxy's relative location in the Universe.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Universe, on the largest cosmic scales, is both:

1. uniform, i.e. the same at all locations
2. isotropic, i.e. the same in all directions

Uniform and isotropic nature of the Universe was explained with Inflation theory by Alan Guth (1979) [1].

Current Cosmological model "Lambda-Cold Dark Matter" estimates that the Universe is made of:

- 68 % dark energy
- 27 % dark matter
- 4.9 % baryonic (normal) matter
- 0.09 % neutrinos
- 0.01 % radiation

II. PROBLEMS WITH "LAMBDA-CDM"-MODEL

- JWST's findings: Distant Galaxy discoveries are not fully explained by age, size and complexity [2]
- Dark Energy: Dark Energy has not been explained and Lambda "constant" is not constant [3]
- Dark Matter: Cold Dark Matter has not been detected
- Hubble Tension: Universe's expansion speed differences with different measurement techniques have not been explained [4]
- Gravitation: "Lambda-CDM"-model does not explain Gravitation

III. NEW "DARK ENERGY-MULTIVERSE"-MODEL

We start with what we know we have to model the Cosmos:

1. Baryonic matter (atom-based "normal matter")
2. Radiation
3. Neutrinos
4. Spacetime (We assume here that "Dark Energy" and "Dark Matter" are both made of Spacetime)

Radiation and Neutrinos have combined max. 0.1 % of the total energy of the Universe so they have very minor role in Universe's energy model.

A. Dark Energy is Spacetime

The key in this theory is the definition of Spacetime i.e. "empty Space":

- Platform of All
- Platform for Atomic Structure
- Platform for Life and Consciousness, at least the "materialistic realization"
- Platform for Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) operations
- Structure is based on Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) theory
- Spacetime is "the Luminiferous Aether"
- Spacetime obeys the Laws of Thermodynamics

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- Total amount of Spacetime in the Universe is fixed from Inflation, only the Volume of Spacetime's Quantas changes due to expansion or compression (Thermodynamics Law I)
- Pressure of empty Spacetime is positive and entropy increases and density decreases as Universe expands (Thermodynamics Law II)
- Expanding empty Spacetime causes light to red-

shift as energy density decreases

- Empty Spacetime behaves like perfect fluid. Conservation of Mass, Momentum and Energy is maintained according to Navier-Stokes Equations for Compressible Fluids in Equation 1 [5].

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \vec{V}}{\partial t} + \vec{V} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \vec{V} \right) = -\vec{\nabla} p - \vec{\nabla} \left(\frac{2}{3} \mu (\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{V}) \right) + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\mu (\vec{\nabla} \vec{V} + (\vec{\nabla} \vec{V})^T)) + \rho \vec{g} \quad (1)$$

Variables:

ρ = density (kg/m^3)

t = time (s)

\vec{V} = velocity vector (m/s)

p = pressure (N/m^2)

μ = dynamic viscosity ($Pa \cdot s$)

\vec{g} = gravitational acceleration (m/s^2)

$\vec{\nabla} \cdot$ = del (gradient) operator ($1/m$)

$\vec{\nabla}$ = divergence operator ($1/m$)

$\vec{V} \cdot \vec{\nabla}$ = advective term operator ($1/s$)

Energy in Atomic structure "inside" Spacetime makes relative Volume of Spacetime "Quantas" smaller and relative size fixed per each different Chemical Element (illustrated in Figure 1) and even Black Hole. "Quantas" of Spacetime are like small loops connected with each other according to Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) theory. Volume changes of Spacetime causes curvature of Spacetime. Quanta of Spacetime that's volume has decreased due to Baryonic matter does not increase pressure of Spacetime with constant ($p \times V$) like in Adiabatic Process with Ideal Gasses.

Relative volume of empty Spacetime "Quanta" changes with Adiabatic Process:

$$pV\gamma = constant \quad (2)$$

p = the pressure of the system

V = the volume of the system

γ = the adiabatic index

- Baryonic matter and Black Holes are curving Spacetime. Curved Spacetime tells matter how to move due to pressure difference of Spacetime as Gravitation
- Massless particles f.e. photons are moving in Spacetime with the speed of light
- In Galaxy scales Spacetime compression creates "Dark Matter halo"

- "Dark Matter" is Spacetime behavior with Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND)
- Universe's volume of collapsed and then inflated Spacetime is a part Multiverse's Spacetime
- Complexity of Spacetime cannot be underestimated in any way, even it appears mainly "empty"
"Spacetime tells matter how to move; matter tells spacetime how to curve." John Wheeler

B. Density of Dark Energy

In current standard cosmology the universe has three components: [6]

- Matter. Energy density scales with the inverse cube of the scale factor, i.e.:

$$\rho \propto^{-3} \quad (3)$$

- Radiation. Energy density scales to the inverse fourth power of the scale factor:

$$\rho \propto^{-4} \quad (4)$$

- Dark Energy. Current understanding: it is an intrinsic property of space and has a constant energy density, regardless of the dimensions of the volume under consideration:

$$\rho \propto^0 \quad (5)$$

Correction:

In this theory we assume the Dark Energy value $\rho \propto^0$ is incorrect. The correct value is the same as with normal Matter $\rho \propto^{-3}$, even it seems counterintuitive. So the scale factor for Dark Energy is:

$$\rho \propto^{-3} \quad (6)$$

FIG. 1. Relative size of spacetime in different atoms

Proof:

Redshift of the light indicates the decreasing energy density of Spacetime when total amount of Spacetime is fixed but volume increases (Thermodynamics Law I & II). Expansion rate of Spacetime's volume is greatest in empty Spacetime areas and smallest in Galaxy centers in the Universe. As the Spacetime expands with decreasing density $\rho \propto^{-3}$ the light is redshifted and light's energy is decreasing to the inverse fourth power of the scale factor $\rho \propto^{-4}$. Spacetime really is "the Luminiferous Aether", the scale is just different than in Michelson-Morley experiment (1887). Since Gravitation is holding Galaxies sizes quite stable the Spacetime's volume in Galaxy does not increase much so we are not able to detect changes in relative volume of Spacetime in Galaxy easily. Different expansion rates in different parts of the Universe is the explanation for Hubble Tension.

The Laser Interferometer Gravitational-Wave Observatory (LIGO) has detected cosmic Gravitational Waves with merging black holes since 2015 [7]. Black holes are causing Gravitational Waves by changing volume of Spacetime when rotating around each another. Changes in volume of Spacetime are causing the detectable phase

difference of laser light beams in LIGO and that is the direct evidence of that the density of Spacetime is not constant.

C. Dark Matter

In Galaxy scales Spacetime compression creates "Dark Matter halo" that is implied by gravitational effects. "Dark Matter" is Spacetime behavior with Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND) presented by Mordehai Milgrom (1983).

Spacetime pressure differences in Galaxy are analogical with air pressure differences in hurricane, both presented in Figure 2 (Hurricane Katrina and Galaxy M74 ©NASA). Adiabatic Process in Equation (2) is visualized in Galaxy disc in Figure 3. With Galaxy disc the Theory of Inverse-Square Law $1/r^2$ does not match, it is $1/r$. The rotating supermassive black hole in Galaxy center keeps spiral arms rotating in equator level and Spacetime outside the Galaxy disc plane without matter keeps the Spacetime pressure towards disc plane so matter is not able to escape.

FIG. 2. Hurricane Katrina and Galaxy M74

FIG. 3. Relative size of spacetime in galaxy

Summary: Dark Matter is compressed Spacetime in Galaxy scales

D. Hubble tension

In Figure 3 and in Figure 4 "Dark Energy-Universe"-model there are visualized the relative size differences of Spacetime "Quantas" in Galaxy and in the Universe. Expansion of the Universe is greatest in empty Spacetime regions and smallest in Galaxy centers. Empty spacetime "Quanta" size obeys the Adiabatic Process. Gravitation in Galaxies is keeping amount of baryonic matter and total volume of Spacetime nearly constant. Spacetime's scale factor is $\rho \propto^{-3}$, but the expansion effect takes place mainly in empty Spacetime regions as the Universe expands inside Multiverse.

Summary: Hubble Tension is the different expansion rates of Spacetime in different parts of the Universe

E. Gravitation

Sir Isaac Newton formulated Gravitation in Principia (1687):

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2} \quad (7)$$

Where:

F = Gravitational force acting between two objects ($kg * m/s^2$)

G = Gravitational constant ($m^3/(kg * s^2)$)

m_1, m_2 = masses of objects (kg)

r^2 = distance squared (m^2)

Henry Cavendish conducted Cavendish experiment (1797) where he calculated the Earth's mass and that experiment later led to definition of Gravitational constant using torsion pendulum to measure the weak gravitational force between small and large lead spheres.

Michelson-Morley experiment (1887) failed to detect the Luminiferous Aether, a medium carrying the light waves. Albert Einstein's Special Relativity (1905) presented the idea that light moves in Spacetime frame with constant speed with no rest mass. Light and gravitational waves have been measured to have the same speed, approximately 299,792,458 meters per second, in a vacuum.

The Adiabatic Process of Spacetime in Equation (2) in Galaxy is illustrated in Figure 3. With this model the pressure difference of Spacetime works as Gravitation for Baryonic matter and Radiation. For Galaxy in Figure 2 and model in Figure 3 with Disc Galaxy in 2D-plane the $1/r$ -inverse ratio in Gravitation is easy to verify with Golden ratio pattern in Galaxy Spiral-structure. Theory of Gravitation as geometrics of Spacetime "Quanta"-spheres in 3D-space with scale factor $\rho \propto^{-3}$ matches consistently with Inverse-Square Law $1/r^2$.

In this approach the conclusion is that the Gravitational constant G is not constant with different distances from the Galaxy center.

Summary: Gravitation is the pressure difference of Spacetime

IV. MULTIVERSE

The James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) has identified distant galaxies that are much more evolved than our current Cosmological Models predict, e.g. Galaxy JADES-GS-z14-0. Distant Galaxy discoveries are not fully explained by age, size and complexity. Over 300 large, bright and highly redshifted galaxies have been discovered. In this article a radical explanation for this problem is presented: The Multiverse.

Multiverse-model assumes that our Universe is a part of bigger volume of Spacetime; i.e. part of the Multiverse. In Figure 4 a new Cosmological model "Dark Energy-Multiverse" is presented in visual format.

Applying the Thermodynamics Law I and II we can make following conclusions:

1. Amount of Spacetime + Energy (Baryonic Matter + Radiation) has been the same in the Universe since Inflation, nothing has been added or lost. Volume of Spacetime in the Universe has increased and is still increasing. Density of empty Spacetime is decreasing due to expansion of Universe.
2. Pressure of empty Spacetime is positive, not negative. Universe's pressure of Spacetime is bigger than pressure of Spacetime in the Multiverse.
3. Entropy of Spacetime in the Universe is increasing due to expansion of Universe.

When pressure of Spacetime in the Universe is bigger than pressure of Spacetime in the Multiverse in Equation (8) so Universe is expanding:

$$p_{univ} > p_{multiv} \quad (8)$$

p_{univ} = pressure of Spacetime in the Universe

p_{multiv} = pressure of Spacetime in the Multiverse

Since some of the Universe's outer region Baryonic material is assumed being attracted by the Multiverse's galaxy superstructures the expansion speed is accelerating.

Summary: Dark Energy is the greater pressure of Spacetime in the inflated Universe compared to the pressure of Spacetime in the Multiverse

A. The Oscillating Universe

The Oscillating Universe Theory presented by Alexander Friedmann (1922) proposed that the Universe undergoes continuous cycles of expansion and contraction,

FIG. 4. Expanding Universe, Dark Energy-Multiverse

starting with a Big Bang and ending in a Big Crunch, after which a new Big Bang begins a new cycle.

In this theory Multiverse-model assumes that our Universe is a part of bigger volume of Spacetime; i.e. part of the Multiverse. Universes are born and collapsing in different parts in the Multiverse.

Our whole Universe's volume of collapsed and then inflated Spacetime is a part Multiverse's Spacetime, illustrated in Figure 4 the collapsed Universe has the same amount of Spacetime and Energy than the Inflated Universe. Spacetime structure is Loop Quantum Gravity. Spacetime is continuous and has no real barrier between Inflated Universe and Multiverse. Spacetime moves gravitational effects and radiation from Multiverse to Universe and vice versa. Empty Spacetime's volume changes exponentially during compression and inflation.

B. Pre-Inflation and Inflation

The "Dark Energy-Multiverse"-model presents three stages before the Inflation:

1. Stable initial stage

Multiverse has a very large unknown volume of Spacetime and Baryonic Matter in it. Assumption is that Multiverse can have diameter of trillions of lightyears. Ratio of Spacetime and Baryonic Matter is assumed to be almost the same both in Multiverse and Universe to keep the system dynamically stable. Quantum mechanical rules are assumed to be the same in Multiverse as in our Universe, because both are having same Spacetime as platform for all Quantum Electrodynamical operations.

2. Universe-scale Gravitation

Due to f.e. Inflation in other part of Multiverse the Baryonic Matter is having a growing concentration in certain area of Multiverse. Galaxy Clusters are starting to attract each other due to Gravitation, forming large Galaxy Supercluster filaments, forming a fullerene shape sphere that contains our Universe amount of Baryonic Matter and Spacetime. Gravitation starts compresses the whole sphere-structure towards Singularity. Universe-scale Gravitation requires enormous amount of Baryonic Matter, equal the amount in our Universe, illustrated in Figure 4, "Universe, -5 billion years old".

3. Collapse of the Universe

At some point the whole Universe's volume of Spacetime starts to compress inside Galaxy clusters sphere, Illustrated in Figure 4, "Universe, -1 billion years old", and finally compressing into a Universe size Black hole having the equal Mass and Spacetime than in our Universe. Schwarzschild radius of Black hole is billions of lightyears having the mass of hundreds of billions of Galaxies. Matter looses

atomic structure in Black hole. Spacetime outside the black hole is having very low density in collapse phase, forming a "false vacuum", term presented by Alan Guth in Inflation Theory. After a critical mass the Inflation starts and our Universe is born, Illustrated in Figure 4, "Universe, 0 year old".

4. Inflation

Inflation starts when the Matter in Black hole reaches critical mass analogically to Atomic Bomb. The Black Hole Matter loses its own structure in Spacetime due to Universe scale compressed Spacetime inside Black Hole with very high Spacetime pressure in Singularity and Energy starts to distribute evenly in Singularity of Spacetime. With critical mass the Spacetime in Singularity starts to expand rapidly as Repulsive Gravitation. Atomic structure does not anymore compress matter towards Singularity with Gravitation and Spacetime with Energy in it is able to expand rapidly. Very low pressure of Spacetime ("false vacuum") outside the Singularity makes rapid expansion possible and Inflation starts, illustrated in Figure 4, "Universe, 1 year old". Inflation ends when Spacetime's rapid expansion in "false vacuum" has ended and Inflated Spacetime meets Superstructures and higher Spacetime pressure in edge of Multiverse, illustrated in Figure 4, "Universe, 1 year old".

C. Scenarios for Multiverse

If the inflated Universe is part of bigger Multiverse there are Three scenarios, visualized in Figure 5:

1. Inflated Spacetime in the Universe continues beyond our visible area and we are only able to see our Inflated Universe
2. Inflated Spacetime in the Universe continues partially beyond our visible area but in some part we can see into the Spacetime volume of the Multiverse beyond the Universe
3. Inflated Spacetime in the Universe is smaller than our observable area and we can see the Spacetime volume of the Multiverse area in any direction beyond the Universe

James Webb Space Telescope's findings:

James Webb Space Telescope is able to see at least in one direction beyond our inflated Universe so scenario 2 or even scenario 3 is valid.

Scenario 1. Inflated spacetime's volume is bigger than visible spacetime's volume

Scenario 2. Inflated spacetime's volume is partially intersecting the visible spacetime's volume

Scenario 3. Inflated spacetime's volume is smaller than visible spacetime's volume

Definitions:

FIG. 5. Scenarios for Multiverse

V. PREDICTIONS

With models previously explained we reach the following predictions:

1. Observations of Superstructures in the Multiverse

JWST is able to see distant, old and evolved galaxies and galaxy filaments in Multiverse region that form large superstructures. Superstructures can be in forms of f.e. rings, arcs, crosses and "spider webs". Biggest superstructures can be billions of lightyears in diameter. Also very old and massive black holes will be observed.

2. Measurement of the size of the Inflated Universe

JWST is able to see the Universe's edge in the Multiverse in different directions and the size of the Inflated Universe is able to be estimated.

3. Measurement of Milky Way's relative location in the Universe

JWST is able to see the Universe's edge in different directions and Milky Way Galaxy's relative location in the Universe is able to be estimated.

VI. REFERENCES

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